

DYNAMICS OF ORGANISED DAIRY INDUSTRY IN GUJARAT: IN CONTEXT TO THE NATIONAL DAIRY PLAN

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Abstract

Dairy sector is characterised by the different types of linkages between the milk producers and dairy processing industry. Gujarat dairy processing industry is backed by a few large cooperatives. A unit level data of NSS, ASI was used (1999-00 to 2015-16) to study the growth of organized dairy industry, performance of organized dairy industry and product diversification in organized dairy industry. The growth rate in terms of number of factories before the National Dairy Plan (1999-00 to 2009-10) is lower (0.67 per cent) than the growth during the National Dairy Plan (2010-11 to 2015-16) i.e. 3.50 per cent. Growth rate of value of output before National Dairy Plan (1999-00 to 2009-10) remained 9.89 per cent whereas during the National Dairy Plan period it registered 14.73 per cent at constant price level (2015-16). Growth rate of gross value addition at constant price level (2015-16) increased at higher level (23.15 per cent) during the National Dairy Plan phase as compared to before National Dairy Plan phase (9.76 percent). Fixed asset formation growth rate was remained 6.53 per cent only before National Dairy Plan whereas during National Dairy Plan it had achieved 31.63 per cent growth. Gross value addition per factory increased 6.84 times over the study period, even though number of factories did not increased much. It infers that there is higher increase in gross value addition over the study period. Gross value addition per labour also increased 4.34 times over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16). However, gross value addition per rupee of fixed asset didn't changed much. Liquid milk was major value added milk product of dairy industry in the 1999-00. However, liquid milk share in total milk products has been reduced to extent of 62.90 and 55.29 per cent over 2010-11 and 2015-16 respectively. In the recent years milk powder (12.04 per cent), cheese (7.71 per cent), butter (6.62 per cent), milk made sweets (6.56 per cent), ice cream (3.31 per cent) and curd (0.50 per cent) had emerged as dairy products in the product portfolio of Gujarat's organized dairy processing industry.

Keywords: Dairy, Organised Industry, Growth, Productivity, Diversification, Gujarat

Introduction

Gujarat state is fifth largest milk producer (7.69 percent in 2017-18) in country. Gujarat state account 5.02 percent of livestock population of country. At the same time Gujarat state account 6.67 percent share of bovine population of India. Out of total 20.17 million bovine population of state buffalo account nearly 50 percent share (DAHD&F, 2018-19). As Gujarat is one of the leading milk processing state in country. Gujarat account 114 organized dairy factories and majority of them based on cooperative model (Singh & Datta, 2018). In Gujarat state economy, share of livestock sector is about 20 per cent of agriculture gross state value addition (GSVA) and it is 3.14 per cent of state GSVA. Whereas, milk sector contribution is around 21 per cent of total value of agriculture output of Gujarat state. Over the last fifteen years (2000-01 to 2015-16) milk production of state has increased around 2.31 times whereas value of milk output increased around 8 times at nominal price level. This trend shows the increasing importance of dairy sector in Gujarat economy (Singh *et al.*, 2019). Dairy processed segment is growing due to increased demand for packaged fluid milk and diversified dairy products. According to NDDDB, the total installed processing capacity of the dairy cooperative sector is approximately 43 million liters per day while the total registered processing capacity of private dairy sector is 73 million liters per day. According to industry estimates around 70 percent of the processed milk is sold as fluid milk with the remaining used in manufacture of value added products. The packaged milk in India is mostly marketed as pasteurized milk in various variants depending on the fat content. Consumption of value added dairy products are experiencing significant annual growth rates of around 15-20 percent due to rising disposable income, urbanization, dual income households and other demographic shifts. This is true for products such as dairy whitener, butter, ghee (clarified butter), paneer (cottage cheese), flavored milk, ice cream, cheese, yogurt, butter milk, and ethnic sweets (Intodia, Vijay., 2017). Fluid milk accounts for the largest product category accounting for approximately 60% of total dairy market. Ghee, paneer and khoa are the three other largest product categories. However, majority of these products are sold in unorganized segment which accounts for more than 90% in these products category (Anon., 2016). The traditional dairy products were mainly manufactured by the unorganized sector where the major manpower resource was from the

family and the raw material was their own input. It should be noted that the unorganized sector utilizes low level of technology and also has low benchmark in quality control measures; but the value addition from this sector is of a great economic significance. Though the percentage of entrepreneurs in the dairy sector is less than one per cent, its coverage has increased from 0.43 per cent to 0.88 per cent between 51st and 56th NSSO rounds. However, coverage of the unorganized dairy sector has improved significantly in terms of value addition. For instance, the unorganized cheese producers which were about 6 per cent in 1994-95, increased to 29 per cent in 2000-01. Similarly, the share of ice cream manufacturers jumped from 6 percent to around 11 per cent during this period. On the other side, the percentage of butter manufacturing units decreased from 1.53 per cent to 0.64 per cent and of ghee making units fell from 13 per cent to 7 per cent during this period (Singh & Datta, 2010).

The development of the dairy industry was seen by Indian policy makers as a measure to create supplementary employment and income in the small and marginal farming house-holds and landless wage earners, they are the important segment of the Indian population. Recently, Government of India under Central Sector Scheme launched National Dairy Plan Phase I (NDP-1) implemented by the National Dairy Development Board through End Implementing Agencies (EIA) for a period of 2011-12 to 2018-19. The major objectives of NDP-1 are to increase the productivity of milch animals and to provide greater market access to the milk producers in the form of organized milk market. In this context it is important to access the tangible achievements of organized dairy processing industry under the NDP-1 phase programme.

The previous discussion highlights the importance of organized dairy industry in Gujarat for dairy development of state. In the light of previous discussion this study confine to the study the growth of organized dairy industry, performance of organized dairy industry and product diversification in organized dairy industry over the study period .

Materials and Methods**Data**

Dairy processing industry refers to the manufacturing sector that processes raw materials from dairy sector. Central Statistics Organization (CSO) conducted each year Annual Survey of Industries

(ASI). In this survey they cover only “Organised Manufacturing” units/factories. The present study was based on secondary data. The unit level data for organised dairy products manufacturing factories was collected from Annual Survey of Industries (ASI). The unit level data provide all manufacturing activity information for individual factory for the period of 1999-2000 to 2015-16. This study used unit level data of ‘Manufacture of Dairy Products’ category of ASI from period of 1999-2000 to 2015-16 of Gujarat state.

Analytical Framework

The Compound Growth Rate (CGR) of the dairy processing industry enables to comprehend the increase or decrease of dairy processing units over the periods. CGR of organised dairy processing units was estimated from time series data for the period 1999-2000 to 2015-16. The exponential growth model used in this study is specified as below:

$$Y_t = ab^t e^\epsilon$$

Where,

Y_t = Number of dairy processing units in t-year

a = Constant term

b = Regression coefficient

t = Time period

ϵ = Error Term

Based on the estimated slope parameter (b), the CAGR (%) was calculated as:

$$\text{CAGR (\%)} = [\text{Antilog of } (b^*) - 1] \times 100$$

Where $b^* = \text{Log } b$

Performance of an industry can be evaluated through many dimensions. There is no unique set of dimensions which can be used to evaluate the performance of an industry. No single performance indicator will provide enough information to determine the health of an industry. Therefore, partial productivity measures were used in this study to evaluate the performance of dairy processing industry. To judge the performance of dairy processing industry in terms of productivity we used the concept of gross value added by per unit/factory, gross value added per employee and gross value added per rupee capital investment. The analysis was carried out for three cross sectional periods (1999-00, 2010-11 and 2015-16) for to examine the dynamics.

To study the product diversification over the study period descriptive analysis was used. The analysis was carried out for three cross sectional periods (1999-00, 2010-11 and 2015-16) for examining the dynamics over the product diversification level. In this study product diversification at industry level was studied by using the value of various products manufactured by the industry.

Results and Discussion

Growth of organized dairy industry

The study of statistic and dynamism nature of an industry over the time period is an important indicator to access the changes in the particular industry. Over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16) various policy, technological and demographical changes has occurred and it all affected various dimensions of the dairy industry. The growth rate of number of dairy factories, value of output, value of input cost and fixed asset formation estimated by using the appropriate WPI deflators for the estimation of real growth rate are presented in the Table 1. Growth rate of value of output before National Dairy Plan (1999-00 to 2009-10) remained 9.89 per cent whereas during the National Dairy Plan period it registered 14.73 per cent. This shows that organized dairy industry has achieved highest output growth during the National Dairy Plan phase. Overall, organized dairy industry observed 10.74 per cent growth in terms of value of output. More or less similar trend was observed in growth rate of value of input cost. However, in organized dairy industry, growth rate of gross value addition increased at higher level (23.15 per cent) during the National Dairy Plan phase as compared to before National Dairy Plan phase (9.76 percent). This reflects the National Dairy Plan became the instrumental for the phenomenal growth of organized dairy industry. This higher growth substantially corroborates with the growth in fixed asset formation in

the respective policy reform period (National Dairy Plan). Overall, fixed asset formation in the organized dairy industry has accelerated with 20.32 per cent annual growth rate.

Table: 1

Performance of organized dairy industry

Previous section highlighted the various growth patterns registered by the Gujarat dairy industry in terms of number of factories, value of output, value of input cost and fixed asset formation. The growth across the various dimensions was partly contributed by partial productivity measures. In this section, we look at the productivity of organised dairy industry over the study period in terms of GVA (Gross Value Addition)/factory, GVA/fixed asset and GVA/labour. It is revealed from the Table-2 that GVA per factory increased 6.84 times over the study period, even though number of factories did not increased much. It infers that there is higher increase in gross value addition over the study period. This shows augmentation pattern of growth in dairy industry. Gross value addition per labour also increased 4.34 times over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16). However, gross value addition per rupee of fixed asset didn't changed much. Even in some recent years, it has reduced drastically. To achieve the higher gross value addition/output over the period, dairy industry require higher capital investment at the backward linkages like bulk chilling facilities, buildings and infrastructure at the cooperative society level, IT enabled technology etc.

Table: 2

Product diversification in organized dairy industry

Dairy industry involves processing raw milk into several value added products. Over the time various factors (technological factor, demographic factors, income changes, consumer taste and preferences etc.) compelled the dairy industry to diversify the products portfolio. In this regard Table-3 presents the dairy industry products portfolio across the three cross sectional time periods i.e. 1999-00, 2010-11 and 2015-16. The result reveals that liquid milk was major value added milk product of dairy industry in the 1999-00. However, liquid milk share in total milk products has been reduced to extent of 62.90 and 55.29 per cent over 2010-11 and 2015-16 respectively. This shows that other milk products have captured the higher share in total dairy products portfolio over the study period. Among the other milk products milk powder continuously gained the higher share over the study period (increased from 10.42 per cent to 12.04 percent over 1999-00 to 2015-16). Similarly, butter share in overall milk products has increased from 3.99 per cent to 6.62 per cent over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16). Cream emerged as new category in the dairy products and it has gained from 0.02 percent to 7.71 per cent share in the dairy products. In the year 1999-00, ghee was one of the major dairy products but its share has reduced to the extent of 5.28 per cent. Cheese was gained the share in overall dairy products from 0.41 per cent to 2.06 per cent over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16). Ice cream and curd also occupied higher share among the value added products of dairy industry. Milk made sweets category gained higher share from 0.43 per cent to 6.56 per cent over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16) in overall dairy products portfolio of dairy industry.

Table: 3

Conclusions

The growth rate in terms of number of factories before the National Dairy Plan (1999-00 to 2009-10) is lower (0.67 per cent) than the growth during the National Dairy Plan (2010-11 to 2015-16) i.e. 3.50 per cent. Growth rate of value of output before National Dairy Plan (1999-00 to 2009-10) remained 9.89 per cent whereas during the National Dairy Plan period it registered 14.73 per cent at constant price level (2015-16). Growth rate of gross value addition at constant price level (2015-16) increased at higher level (23.15 per cent) during the National Dairy Plan phase as compared to before National Dairy Plan phase (9.76 percent). Fixed asset formation growth rate was remained 6.53 per cent only before National Dairy Plan whereas during National Dairy Plan it had achieved 31.63 per cent growth. Gross value addition per factory increased 6.84 times over the study period, even though

number of factories did not increased much. It infers that there is higher increase in gross value addition over the study period. Gross value addition per labour also increased 4.34 times over the study period (1999-00 to 2015-16). However, gross value addition per rupee of fixed asset didn't changed much. Gross value addition per factory and gross value addition per labour are the guiding force for the improvement of performance of dairy processing industry. At the same time industry is to cautiously take the decision of capital investment. Liquid milk was major value added milk product of dairy industry in the 1999-00. However, liquid milk share in total milk products has been reduced to extent of 62.90 and 55.29 per cent over 2010-11 and 2015-16 respectively. In the recent years milk powder (12.04 per cent), cheese (7.71 per cent), butter (6.62 per cent), milk made sweets (6.56 per cent), ice cream (3.31 per cent) and curd (0.50 per cent) had emerged as dairy products in the product portfolio of Gujarat's organized dairy processing industry. Under the aegis of National Dairy Plan organized dairy industry in Gujarat gained a lot in terms mainly fold increase in output and capital investment at industry level. This national project could be the guiding force for Gujarat dairy industry to move this industry into the new growth trajectory.

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Table 1: Growth rate (%) across the different parameters of organized dairy industry in Gujarat (At constant price of 2015-16)

Year	No. of factories	Value of Output	Value of Input	Value of Gross Value Addition	Value of Fixed Asset
1999-00 to 2009-10	0.67	9.89	10.41	9.76	6.53
2010-11 to 2015-16	3.50	14.73	13.66	23.15	31.63
1999-00 to 2015-16	1.60	10.76	10.85	12.10	16.12

Table 2: Partial productivity measures over the time (1999-00 to 2015-16) in the organised dairy industry in Gujarat

Years	GVA/Factory (Rs. in Million)	GVA/Labour (Rs. in Million)	GVA/Fixed Asset
1999-00	33.15	0.41	0.74
2000-01	186.33	13.74	4.49
2001-02	52.58	0.66	1.15
2002-03	70.55	0.76	1.28
2003-04	62.65	0.71	1.20
2004-05	85.07	0.76	1.75
2005-06	107.85	1.04	2.37
2006-07	54.03	0.59	1.52
2007-08	62.41	0.63	1.60
2008-09	165.75	1.48	1.89
2009-10	219.20	1.83	1.91
2010-11	162.37	1.25	1.38
2011-12	105.48	0.95	0.84
2012-13	116.27	1.15	0.69
2013-14	406.96	3.06	1.82
2014-15	302.81	2.17	0.99
2015-16	226.67	1.78	0.64

Note: Ratios calculated at constant price of 2015-16.

Table 3: Product diversification in organized dairy industry

Name of Dairy Product	1999-00	2010-11	2015-16
Liquid Milk	66.27	62.90	55.29
Milk Powder	10.42	13.39	12.04
Butter	3.99	-	6.62
Cream	0.02	1.65	7.71
Ghee	10.88	12.30*	5.28
Cheese	0.41	0.36	2.06
Ice Cream	-	2.67	3.31
Curd	0.21	0.63	0.50
Milk Made Sweets	0.43	-	6.56
Other Milk Products	7.35	6.1	-

*2010-11 Ghee is not absolute category but it was Butter and other fats and oils derived from milk.